

Literature Review on Rent Seeking Behavior of Political Authorities

Assoc. Prof. Mustafa Ergenekon AVCI

To cite this article: Mustafa Ergenekon AVCI, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 91 – 102. - 0099-0001-2209-0203.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

Externalities, the provision of public goods, monopolistic behavior and imperfect competition are some examples of market failure concerns that contribute to an inefficient economy (Acemoğlu and Robinson, 2013). Fundamental economic policy changes can be made at the national level (for example, through stabilization policies and structural adjustments) and at the sectoral level (through examples such as agriculture, industry, and trade) as a solution to this inefficiency. (Adams, 2000; World Bank, 2008). Reforms in economic policy can result in both winners and losers overall. Because of the diversity of group interests and the unclear benefits to the group, there are social groupings that advocate delaying or accelerating the implementation of policy changes (Adams, 2000). As a result, significant changes took place in the political balance of the society (Acemoğlu & Robinson, 2013). Political economy models of proposed changes in economic policy According to Pederson (1997) and Adams (two thousand), parties representing the government and the public sector (such as policy makers and practitioners) and private groups (eg, workers, capitalists, farmers, etc.) students, etc.), this issue is noteworthy as they foresee an increase in their returns. State parties engage in rent-seeking behavior to sell their

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political authority, and private organizations are interested in buying political influence. Private organizations bribe government parties to delay or speed up the process of making policy choices (Pederson, 1997; Adams, 2000). The choice to undertake policy changes rests with the ruling elite, and this decision is influenced by both their own interests and the degree of political stability in the environment (Adam 2000). There is a lack of clarity among those responsible for making decisions about the overall advantages of policy, how these benefits will be redistributed, and the position of the elements of production in the economy after changes (Adam, 2000). These unpredictability may result in a political risk, and the political establishment will not make the decision to change policies if it perceives that its authority is at stake. But if this process results in a Nash equilibrium, the benefits of policy improvements are shared equally among all groups. Consequently, when it comes to the policy reform process, it is essential to consider the effects of redistribution, the political regime, and the economic and political stability in the country during the implementation of the reform.

Keywords: *Monopolistic Behavior, Imperfect Competition, An Inefficient Economy, Political Equilibrium, Policy Improvement*

1. Introduction

Reforms in public policy and the effects of redistribution Alsina and Rodrik (1994) state that the distribution of productive resources in a society is an important factor in determining the demand for policy change. Lower property rights and greater economic inequality seek to stifle the expansion of the economy (Alina and Rodrick, 1994; Persson and Tabellini, 1994; Clark, 1995). On the other hand, the political regime is responsible for determining the redistribution policies as well as the property rights of the people. The following sections discuss the effects of redistribution brought about by structural adjustment policies and stabilization measures. Macroeconomic conditions are the focus of stabilization policies, which include measures such as improving the balance of payments, controlling inflation and depreciation of the currency (Adms, 2000; Easterly, 2003). The depreciation of the currency provides a rapid increase in costs

(Herbst, 1990). On the other hand, Central Bank Independence (CBI) has the potential to significantly reduce inflation, provided the level of government spending remains relatively stable (Acemoglu, Johnson, Querubin & Robinson, 2008). However, reducing the amount of money the government spends can have a serious impact on some underprivileged groups. Adjustments to the structure of the economy usually consist of privatization and promotion of the private sector, reducing trade barriers, promoting exports and discouraging import-substituting businesses, as well as removing price and interest rate controls (Adms, 2000). ; Easter, 2003). If import substitution businesses are discouraged by privatization, there is a possibility of a temporary increase in unemployment (Herbst, 1990). According to Easterly (2003), structural adjustment policies are less beneficial in reducing poverty, as the poor employed in the informal sector will earn less from changes implemented in the formal sector. As a result, programs for the transfer of aid need to be designed so that they can target vulnerable populations (Easterly, 2003).

2. Economic Policy Under Various Different Political Regimes

Reforms in economic policy under a variety of different political regimes The political system is the single most important factor in determining whether policy improvements are effective. The democratic political system has a destabilizing effect on ongoing economic changes (Gordon, 1996). Policy changes in a democratic society can pose a high political risk to the government, which can lead to delays in policy reform choices. This is true even though political liberalization reduces the limits of economic development (Gordon, 1996). Meanwhile, Marangos (2005) argues that significant economic changes cannot be achieved without at least some degree of political participation at a minimum. In democratic systems, the election held at the ballot box has an impact on the redistribution and thus on economic development (Alina and Rodrik, 1994). After the implementation of policy changes, slower economic development is due to a high level of democracy. Compared to shorter political regimes, longer ones are associated with slower economic development (Jong-A-Ping, De Haan, 2007). In addition, ideological polarization also affects redistribution policies (Alisina and Tabellini, 1989).

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3. A Democratic System

Unlike a democratic system, an authoritarian government does not allow its citizens' voting preferences to have any influence on policy improvements implemented. Optimal timing to make policy changes If an economy is experiencing a crisis, it indicates that the economy is in a Pareto-inferior state and the policies currently in place are not supported. The ideal moment to implement reform measures is now (Drazen & Grilli, 1993; Rodrik, 1996). The country's capacity to maintain political stability makes it easier for stakeholders to make collective decisions (Cukierman, Edward & Tabellini, 1992). When a country's political climate is unstable, the implementation of policy improvements during this period can sometimes result in the country falling into a lower position. 3. Concluding remarks Countless nations around the world serve as illustrative examples that clearly demonstrate the importance of political and economic relations in the process of economic change. Both South Korea and Taiwan have emphasized the importance of international assistance in their ongoing economic reforms (Rodrik, Grossman & Norman, 1995). Both of these nations are involved in currency depreciation, export promotion, subsidies to certain industries, massive public expenditure on infrastructure and human capital development, etc. It made these changes, among other policy changes, including (Rodrik, Grossman & Norman, 1995; Rodrik, 1996). According to Rodrik (1996), inequality in these countries in the 1950s was quite low and the workforce was educated. This was the case even though these nations were thriving at the time. Because of their low levels of inequality, the governments of these countries did not place a significant emphasis on redistributive programs and instead carried out the necessary economic reforms. Heads of political parties watched the behavior of government bureaucrats carefully, and a number of educated government officials encouraged private initiative (Rodrik, 1996). The successful implementation of economic reforms in South Korea, Taiwan and other East Asian countries has brought to light the critical role played by consistent political leadership in the expansion of an economy. Using examples from Mexico, Newell (2011) demonstrates the importance of politics in the economic expansion process. From 1935 to the late 1980s, the pace of economic

expansion in Mexico was well above average. However, weak government policies such as the overvaluation of the peso enacted in the 1970s and early 1980s led to more government spending while deterring private sector activity. As a result, the driving force behind the crises between 1976 and 1982 was the economy (Nowell, 2011). Acemoğlu and Robinson (2013) draw attention to the experience of currency devaluation in Ghana, highlighting the fact that some effective economic solutions are not politically meaningful. In 1971, the Ghana government's decision to devalue the country's currency in order to improve the country's balance of payments and its position in the foreign exchange market caused another political leader to seize power. Acemoglu et al. (2008), the implementation of many policy changes can have a seesaw effect. For example, if the government tries to control inflation by imposing measures while incurring massive government spending, the nation cannot control inflation. According to Alisina and Drazen (1991), even if a policy improves the efficiency of the economy, it may be difficult to implement if it has a major negative impact on distribution. The creation and implementation of economic policies is absolutely necessary for the growth and growth of the economy. Any economic policy will have a distributional effect, meaning that it will either create losers or winners and ultimately change the political balance in society. As a result, members of the ruling class tend to continue to serve in their current positions, postponing the implementation of fundamental changes in economic policy.

If a Nation Is Politically Stable

According to research, if a nation is politically stable, the probability of losing power is very low, so the government has the ability to make policy changes. If the country is experiencing a crisis such as foreign debt crises, inflation crises, financial crises, economic collapse or high levels of inequality, it is a good moment to pursue economic reform programs (Agnello, Casreo, Jalles & Sousa, 2015). Therefore, and as a result, successful economic changes need to be politically sound and it is vital to consider the nation's redistributive impact, political regime, economic situation, and political stability. It is common knowledge among sociologists, anthropologists, and political scientists that economics is the social science with the greatest

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political weight. For example, in the United States, economists control influential institutions such as the Federal Reserve and hold positions in every department of the executive and legislative branches of government. On the other hand, every economist is aware that such an effect, if any, is limited to a very small degree. Even if economists speak with one voice, politics will eventually prevail over economic understanding. This is true regardless of the crisis in Europe or the policies around climate change. These wildly different perceptions are so extreme that they practically become caricatures. However, this raises a very important question:

What impact does the economy have on politics?

- a. literatures on the role of economists in policy making and offer fruitful topics for the direction of future work. There are three findings that researchers in sociology, political science, and science and technology studies all agree on. To begin with, economists are likely to be strong advisers in situations believed to be technical, as well as in situations that are ill-defined and where uncertainty forces policymakers to seek new answers.
- b. Second, the direct role economists play in policy making may not be as important as the indirect impact of economics on policy making. The proliferation of economic language causes non-economist policy makers to rethink their understanding of a particular issue. The proliferation of technological tools used by economists affects the information available to policy makers, which in turn changes the decision-making process.
- c. *Third, the political impact of the economy is influenced by intermediate social orders. The actions of economists in the political arena need to be interpreted in light of the dynamics of their semi-autonomous and more globalized disciplines. Similarly, given that the state is made up of several small organizations, organizational dynamics determine whether and how economists influence certain policy areas. These new insights serve as a foundation on which to build a revised research plan.*

We advocate rethinking the issue in light of Eyal and Buchholz's (2010) suggestion of a “sociology of interventions” that inspired our way of thinking. "How does the economy affect policy?" instead of asking, "What must be accomplished for economists and the economy to have an impact on policy?" we have to ask. We strive to solve this problem by providing a basic framework for doing this. Our aim is not to explain why a particular set of economic evidence prevailed at a particular time and place (such as the victories of neoliberalism in the late twentieth century; see mediating the abilities, ideas, and tools of economists to influence policy in a variety of settings. In the tradition of the scientific sociology of knowledge (Bloor, 1991 [1976]), our approach is symmetrical, which means that we analyze the success and failure of certain economic interventions regardless of current perceptions of how accurate they are. This falls within the tradition of Bloor's sociology of scientific knowledge. The patterns we uncover are mostly in the United States throughout the twentieth century. It is derived from empirical research conducted in the United States and Western Europe , but we briefly discuss the extent to which these models can be applied to other parts of the world.

4. The Growing of the Economy as a Global Profession

Although the economy is increasingly becoming a global profession (Fourcade, 2006), its effects will always be mediated by local political institutions. These effects can take different forms in countries with strong domestic economic traditions, such as China and the countries that formed the former Soviet Bloc, and in countries not governed by bureaucratic democratic systems. The difficulty of defining exactly what we mean when we talk about economists is also taken into account by our reformulation. In this context, we are less concerned with the definitional debates surrounding the profession itself (Fourcade, 2009) and more concerned with the aggregation level of policy-making analyses. For example, is it individual economists to consider, ideologically united networks of economists, or the profession as a whole? Do we want to explore the impact of economic theories, economic realities, or economic models instead? We find various answers to these problems in many of the literature studies we have searched, and although we map these variations, we cannot completely resolve them. The question is cut in half

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by our proposed agenda. We distinguish three channels through which economists and economics can influence public policy: professional authority, institutional stance, and cognitive infrastructure. After that, we offer a proposal for dividing the problem into analytical parts. To begin with, how exactly is each of these accomplished, and what role do economists play in the procedure? Second, if a change occurs in the position of professional authority, the stance of an institution, or the cognitive infrastructure, how does this affect politics? The term "professional authority" refers to the general condition of the field of economics as a whole, which varies depending on the historical context and geographical location (Bernstein, 2001; Fourcade, 2009).

In the seventeenth century there was no such thing as a professional economist, nor any university seat devoted to the study of political economy. By the middle of the twentieth century, economics had established itself as a respected and well-funded subject of study. It could be found as a department in every major institution and was seen to have a set of intellectual tools that were both practical and rigorous. In many different ways, the possibility of effective interventions is conditioned by the competent professional status of the economy. The presence of economists in policy-making organizations or networks of influential people is called their "institutional position". In this context, the line between economists and policy makers blurs, and economists may find themselves in a position to personally make policy choices and advise others on how to do so. For example, economists often have an almost unlimited ability to set the course of monetary policy, as a result of their institutional position as head of central banks in many countries. Economists are responsible for managing transnational institutions such as the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund. These organizations are responsible for setting the parameters and constraints within which national governments should operate (Babb, 2007; Chwieroth, 2010). On a more local scale, a wide variety of government agencies have some official offices devoted to economic research. This ensures that the voice of economists is at least heard, if not considered by decision makers in such institutions. Consequently, the term "cognitive infrastructure" refers not only to the development of economic policy tools that provide information and aid decision making, but also to patterns of economic thought prevalent among policy-making elites. Their reasoning (Hacking, 1992) can be compared to the basic

principles and methods of dealing with issues that Reay (2012) found among US economists. Hacking's work focused on the way economists think.

5. This Kind of Reasoning in Schools of Law or Politics

While Reay focuses on PhDs in economics, a more moderate form of economic reasoning is common among policymakers. Many of these policy makers have been exposed to this type of reasoning in law or policy schools (Allison, 2006; Teles, 2008). Even if policymakers choose to ignore certain recommendations made by trained economists, economic style can still influence the way they tackle challenges. Economic policy tools (cf. Muniesa et al., 2007) include a wide range of sociotechnical tools that help policymakers see the world in economic terms and make choices about it. These devices are also called "economic policy instruments". These are devices that produce information that helps us see the economic world, such as the gross domestic product, the inflation rate, or the unemployment rate ; and techniques that assist the policy decision-making process, such as cost-benefit analysis, procedures for auctioning the electromagnetic spectrum, or guidelines for evaluating when mergers are economically efficient. For example, GDP, inflation rate or unemployment rate. The use of policy devices has garnered a relatively low amount of attention from academics. Scholars for science and technology studies (STS) have looked at how economists' devices affect markets rather than policy. This is because political scientists and sociologists have focused on discussions on prominent issues rather than incorporating tools into bureaucracies. We look at several different relevant literatures to explain the influence of economists on public policy . We review literature on epistemic communities, as well as intellectual and political literature from the field of political science; We search professions and specialist literature from the sociology field, and from the STS field, we explore multiple lines of research. We build on these to suggest that economists and economics can have an impact on policy by increasing their professional authority, acquiring positions of institutional power, or reshaping the cognitive infrastructure of policy making through reasoning styles or policy tools. These are all ways in which politics is influenced by economists and the economy.

2. Perspectives on the impact of non-competitive economists 2.1 Politics and political ideas

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Since the 1980s, political sociologists and political scientists have focused most of their theoretical attention on the role that ideas play in politics. The assertion that state elites have an autonomous role in policy making and are not merely agents of class struggle gave rise to this movement (Block, 1977; Evans et al., 1985).

6. The Difficulty and Unpredictability of Policy Making

If state elites have interests and capabilities that are distinct from their class allies, then state elite beliefs are crucial to the causal explanation of policy (Weir and Skocpol, 1985). This research group emphasized the difficulty and unpredictability of policy making and the consequent need for concepts that could condense existing policy options to a more manageable number (Kingdon, 1984; Hall, 1989; Blyth, 2002). Since then, a significant body of research has shown that ideas matter; however, opinions continue to be divided on what exactly ideas are and how they matter (Mehta, 2010).

gone beyond these arguments for the causal power of ideas based on "evidence-of-existence", by addressing issues of whether and why concepts matter (Major, 2010). According to Vivien Schmidt's definition, all politics are to some extent founded on concepts. As this is the case, "the biggest challenge for students of ideas is why some concepts become the policies, programs, and ideologies that dominate political reality and why others do not" (2008, p. 307). The 'ideas' discussed in this research group tend to cluster around various levels of analysis, from macro-level economic paradigms (such as the rise and fall of Keynesianism ; Hall, 1989; Blyth) (Campbell, 1998, 2002). , 2002; Lindvall, 2009) to precise levels of well-defined policy instruments such as interest rate ceilings (Hall, 1993; Anderson, 2008). Although the analysis mostly focuses on the interest group or professional community that drives a particular thought, the actor in this literature is the idea itself (Weir, 1993; Berman, 1998; Parsons, 2003). The aim here is to show, by way of example, how Keynesianism became the dominant economic theory, not how Keynesians advanced their agenda. A significant amount of research in this area has focused on the ways in which certain ideas manifest themselves in different ways depending on

local political, economic and social conditions. Not only did Keynesianism have varying degrees of influence in various nations (to continue the example), but completely different aspects were adopted in countries like Sweden compared to countries like England. For example (Hall, 1989). Subsequent research on the worldwide impact of neoliberal economic theories also highlighted the extent to which their acceptance was influenced by national contexts. This was done for the same reason (Babb, 2001; Fourcade-Gourinchas & Babb, 2002; Ban & Blyth, 2013). This argument perhaps culminates in Campbell and Pedersen's recent (2014) argument that the production and impact of such ideas is national-specific, and that paradigms evolve and coexist more frequently rather than changing dramatically.

This argument culminates in Campbell and Pedersen's recent (2014) argument that the production of such ideas as well as their effects are nationally specific (see also Schneiberg, 2007). In addition to focusing on the interaction of ideas, institutions, and politics, this research group places particular emphasis on three aspects that determine when and how economists' views influence public policy. Above all, they are important because of the role they play in the formation of political interests, and this can only make sense in light of people's understanding of how the world works (Dobbin and Dowd, 2000; Blyth, 2002; Anderson). , 2008). Second, the importance of the ideas proposed by economists varies depending on the degree to which the political climate remains stable. Ideas tend to recede more into the background during periods of relative stability. In times of crisis, the uncertainty of the relationship between a proposed policy and its expected impact, and the variety of options now available, make room for ideas that have the potential to make a difference (Blyth, 2002). . Third, the factors that determine how well an economist's ideas will be implemented vary depending on the degree of analysis used. According to research by Hall (1993) et al (Campbell, 2002; Lindvall, 2009), changes in policy paradigms are more likely to be driven by electoral policies, but changes in technical ideas (which policy tools to use in which settings) are more likely to be chosen by experts.

2.2 Epistemic communities

The literature on ideas and politics treats 'ideas', both broadly and narrowly, as actors with the potential to influence policy, while a closely related literature focusing on international relations takes 'epistemic communities' (Haas, 1989, 1992) as its agent. In this

literature , 'ideas' can be thought of in a broad or narrow sense. Epistemic communities are online groups of knowledgeable people who agree on a common set of knowledge or values. They have more ideological coherence than an entire profession, and as a result, they are in a better position to strategically push policies that align with their ideas. Identifying the conditions under which epistemic communities can produce such an impact is the central organizing principle of the relevant literature . 2 On the other hand, the explanatory capacity of the framework is somewhat limited as a result of the assumption of a reasonably unified collective actor with shared views on how its knowledge should be used for policy (Carstensen, 2011).

Although this research group does not concentrate solely on the epistemic community of economists (although see Ikenberry, 1992), some of their results seem applicable in this context. For example, many scholars in the intellectual and political tradition have considered neoliberalism as a new economic paradigm . On the other hand, there is a vocal group that wants us to see neoliberalism as an epistemic community, a 'collective thought' that includes policy advocates, businessmen and other influential actors as well as some economists (Mirowski and Plehwe, 2009). Neoliberalism, or any other body of ideas held by some economists, can be seen as the foundation of an epistemic community, not a representation of an economic paradigm . This understanding provides a separate way to monitor the impact of neoliberalism on politics. The capacity of an epistemic community to influence policy change is a function of its resources, including support from other powerful players (such as business, unions, the media or other elites) and institutional reach. This also applies to any interest group (Campbell, 1998). Consequently, we have to speculate that the resources that networks of consensus economists can control will determine the level of policy impact that such networks exert. It is also more likely to succeed for epistemic communities when promoting legislation that covers issues for which politicians have limited understanding and weak attitudes. Therefore, economists need to have less direct influence over well-defined, widely publicized, and politically controversial (Ikenberry, 1992), for example tax policy (Feldstein, 1994). In line with research on the relationship between ideas and politics, epistemic communities are more likely to influence the

choice of policy tools and the parameters in which they operate, but less likely to influence actual policy objectives. Anderson, 2008; Lindvall, 2009).

7. Literature on the Epistemic Community

Both research on ideas and policy and the literature on the epistemic community seem to imply that economists who promote certain ideas are best regarded as just another interest group, although a group that draws on the source of professional or scientific authority. The success of economists will be determined by their capacity to forge alliances with influential and resource-rich players, as well as the extent to which the current moment in political institutions and history is conducive to the ideas they are trying to promote. When we consider economists as another interest group that supports a set of ideas, we learn less about how economists therefore differ from other interest groups. While this approach is highly productive for explaining the role that ideas play in shaping certain political outcomes, treating economists as just another interest group tells us less about how economists differ from other interest groups.

2.3 Professions and specialties Although the professions and specialist literature is based on sociology and not political science, it shares with the epistemic community literature an emphasis on specific groups structured around a common body of knowledge. This is something that distinguishes the two post types. Since the 1970s, he has emphasized how professionals obtain and maintain market dominance for a specific set of activities linked to soft information (Larson, 1977; Freidson, 1986; Abbott, 1988). More recently, a resurgent scholarship on experts (Eyal, 2006; Fourcade, 2009; Medvetz, 2012; Eyal, 2013; Stampnitzky, 2013) has also examined how and in what ways professions produce knowledge. These studies are Eyal, 2013; Fourcade, 2009; Medvetz, 2012; Eyal, 2013 and Stampnitzky, 2013. Research on occupations looks only from an environmental perspective at how professionals influence public policy. Steven Brint made a request in 1990 to investigate the circumstances that determined whether professionals had greater or lesser influence on policy, but his request was not followed up systematically. Thus, our observations of the ways professions affect policy are inductive rather than representing clear agreement. Still, we come to a few conclusions that seem applicable to the professional influence

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of economists on government policy. Considering the effects of economists on politics, it is possible that the first institutions that come to mind are the Federal Reserve or the International Monetary Fund. However, research on various professions reveals that the most important influence of economists on politics can be achieved through indirect methods and informal channels, not through advisory duties or official policy functions (Brint, 1990, p. 371). It is more important that experts define problems and establish agendas (O'Connor, 2001; Eyal et al., 2010) than experts advise politicians on what to do (Eyal et al., 2010). (Bernstein, 2001). It can also be thought that economists will have the most impact when they can define some policy issues basically technically (Brint, 1990, pp. 373-374). This may give them the ability to transform their technical authority into moral authority (Kevles, 1978; Halliday, 1987; Bernstein, 1995) or give them the opportunity to make normative choices that are hidden from the view of non-experts because they seem purely technical (Jacob, 1988; O'Connor, 2001; Steensland). , 2006). Both of these possibilities have been the subject of research. On the other hand, and according to research in political science, the more explicitly political an issue is, the less likely independent economists are to influence the results of their policy decisions (Bernstein, 2001). Since the two are somehow autonomous but related ecologies (Abbott, 2005) or fields with their own norms and incentives (Bourdieu, 1988), the policy activity of economists must also be interpreted with reference to their own professional field. It is possible for economists working in the field of politics to operate in the professional field as well. If this is the case, economists' policy actions are likely to reflect the professional field's position on what types of knowledge are considered essential, high-status, or legitimate (Breslau, 1998; Babb, 2001; Mudge and Vauchez). , 2012; Ray, 2012). However, because these two fields are only partially independent of each other, economic concepts such as the 'Laffer curve' can be influential in politics, although it is ignored by academics (Berman & Milanes-Reyes, 2013). In addition, economists may take a unified position on trade liberalization, for example, without building similar consensus among policy makers (Chorev, 2007). Finally, the global policy hypothesis (Meyer et al., 1997; Drori et al., 2003) emphasizes the role of transnational organizations in the diffusion of world culture. These organizations include science and the professions. Although national distinctions continue to exist (Fourcade, 2009), the American economic model has become widespread and has often

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replaced more traditional forms of regional knowledge (Babb, 2001; Dezalay and Garth, 2002). ; Fourcade, 2006). At the same time, however, this process often results in the production of new, hybrid forms of knowledge, especially in countries that maintain robust internal economic traditions (Bockman and Eyal, 2002; Bockman, 2011). This process differs from country to country (Dezalay & Garth, 2002; Fourcade-Gourinchas & Babb, 2002; Montecinos & Markoff, 2010; Ban & Blyth, 2013). 3 Halliday and Carruthers' (2009) studies on the legal profession suggest that countries that are more dependent on transnational organizations for resources are more likely to formally adopt and actually implement their legal mandates. Although many of these differences must be explained by ideographic factors, this finding has at least some resonance with studies in economics (Fourcade-Gourinchas and Babb, 2002).

8. Conclusion

Methods used in scientific research The literature on ideas and politics sees 'ideas' as an actor capable of changing policy, while the literature on epistemic communities and the literature on occupations focuses on groups of people. However, the function of sociotechnical tools is explored in a fourth approach to the problem. Literature on performance and social studies of finance (Callon, 1998b; Beunza and Stark, 2004; MacKenzie, 2006), sociological literature on technical processes such as quantification, accounting, and market design (Carruthers and Espeland, 1991; Espeland and Stevens 2008; Lampland, 2010). ; MacKenzie, 2011; Breslau, 2013) and the entire anthropological literature on expert discourses and their governance implications (Ferguson, 1990; Miller & Rose, 1990; Scott, 1998). They are all concerned with the same thing: the assembly, stability, and effects of sociotechnical tools defined as "knowledge creation methods, criteria, and technical applications". Methodologies used in scientific research begin with the premise that it is impossible to grasp the influence of people or information alone. Rather, the actor capable of influencing policy is a stable pattern of interaction between different elements such as people, knowledge, and the material environment. These sociotechnical communities are referred to by us as "policy tools", using a term from Callon et al. (2007). This research group asks, "Do economists set policies?" produced a series of discoveries that

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contributed to the answer to the question . The impact of the techniques used by economists might be thought to be complex and unexpected. This has been highlighted in all research, from the enormous failure of the Thaba-Tseka livestock improvement project described by Ferguson (1990) to the unintended consequences of US prison penal reform discussed by Espeland and Vannebo (2007). The performativity and counter-performativity sequence, which MacKenzie (2006) found to be valid as the Black-Scholes-Merton model, has been put into practice in financial markets. If economic information is considered reliable, it also has the potential to be performative in the sense that it can influence the actions of the people exposed to it (Callon, 1998a; MacKenzie, 2003; MacKenzie and Millo, 2003). When it comes to monitoring performance, the most profitable positions are probably markets and more specifically financial markets. However, policy choices can also have performance repercussions. For example, America has used the services of game theorists to help develop auctions. As a kind of response, telecommunications companies have also engaged game theorists who help businesses behave in ways predicted by game theory (Guala, 2001; Nik-Khah, 2008). More studies are needed in the literature on this subject .

9. References

- Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, JA (2013). Economics versus Politics: Pitfalls of Policy Advice.
- Acemoglu, D., Johnson, S., Querubin, P., & Robinson, JA (2008). When Does Policy Reform?
- Adam , RH (two thousand). The Politics of Economic Policy Reforms in Developing Countries. policy
- Agnello,L.,Castro,V.,Jalles,JT, & Sousa,RM(2015). What decides the likelihood of?
- Alisina, A., & Drazen, A. (1991). Why Are Stabilizations Delayed? American Economics
- Alisina, A., & Rodrik,D. (1994).Distributive Politics and Economic Growth. quarterly

- Alisina, A., & Tabellini, G. (1989). External Debt, Capital Flight, and Political Risk. NBER American Economic Review. 82(3). 537-555.
- Clark, GRG (1995). More Evidence on Income Distribution and Growth. Journal of Development Economics. 47,403-427.
- Cukierman, A., Edwards, S., & Tabellini, G. (1992). Siegniorage and Political Instability. American Economic Review. 83(3). 598-607.
- Drezen, A., & Grilli, V. (1993). The Benefits of Crises for Economic Reforms. ("The Impact of Politics in Policy Reforms - LMU") American Economic Review. 83(3). 598-607.
- Easterly, W. (2003). IMF and World Bank Structural Adjustment Programs and Poverty. the American Economic Review. 83(3). 598-607.
- Frankel, University Press of Chicago.
- Gordon, DF(1996). Sustaining Economic Reform under Political Liberalization in Africa: Herbst, J. (1990). The Structural Adjustments of Politics in Africa. World Development. 18(7). Issues and Implications. World Development. 24(9).1527-1537.
- Jong-A-Pin, R., & De Haan, J., (2007). Political regime change, economic reform, and growth Journal of Economics. 109(2).465-490.
- Lindblom CE The Science of "Muddling Through," Public Administration Review, 1959, vol. 19 (pg. 79-88)
- Lindvall J. The Real but Limited Influence of Expert Ideas, World Politics, 2009, vol. 61 (pg. 703-730)
- MacKenzie D., Millo Y. Constructing a Market, Performing Theory, American Journal of Sociology, 2003, vol. 109 (pg. 107-145)
- MacKenzie D., Muniesa F., Siu L., Do Economists Make Markets? On the Performativity of Economics, 2007 Princeton University Press Major A. Monetary Orders, Financial Dependence, and Idea Selection: The International

- Constraints on American Monetary Policy, 1961–1963, Political Power and Social Theory, 2010, vol. 21 (pg. 49-92)
- MacKenzie D., An Engine, Not A Camera: How Financial Models Shape Markets, 2006CambridgeMIT Press (“An Engine, not a Camera: How Financial Models Shape Markets, Donald ...”)
- MacKenzie D. An Equation and Its Worlds: Bricolage, Exemplars, Disunity and Performativity in Financial Economics, Social Studies of Science, 2003, vol. 33 (pg. 831-868) (“Evolução da pesquisa em finanças: epistemologia, paradigm e críticas”)
- MacKenzie D. The Credit Crisis as a Problem in the Sociology of Knowledge, American Journal of Sociology, 2011, vol. 116 (pg. 1778-1841) (“Demarche dos dispositivos: apontamentos sobre ordens, convergências e ...”)
- Managing Currency Crises in Emerging Markets. Edited by Michael P. Dooley and Jeffrey A. Mansfield E. Contribution of R&D to Economic Growth in the United States, Science, 1972, vol. 175 (pg. 477-486) March J., Simon H. , Organizations, 1958OxfordWiley
- Marangos, J. (2005). A Political Economy Approach to the Neoclassical Gradualist Model of
- McNeely CL. , Constructing the Nation-State: International Organization and Prescriptive Action, 1995Westport, CTGreenwood PressMedvetz T. , Think Tanks in America, 2012ChicagoUniversity of Chicago PressMehta J. Béland D., Cox RH The Varied Roles of Ideas in Politics, Ideas and Politics in Social Science Research, 2010OxfordOxford University Press(pg. 23-46)Meyer J., Boli J., Thomas GM, Ramirez FO World Society and the Nation State, American Journal of Sociology, 1997, vol. 103 (pg. 144-181)
- Miller P., Rose N. Governing Economic Life, Economy, and Society, 1990, vol. 19 (pg. 2-31)

- Millo Y., MacKenzie D. The Usefulness of Inaccurate Models: Towards an Understanding of the Emergence of Financial Risk Management, Accounting, Organizations, and Society, 2009, vol. 34 (pg. 638-653) (“The usefulness of inaccurate models: Towards an understanding of the ...”)
- Mirowski P., Plehwe D., The Road from Mont Pelerin: The Making of the Neoliberal Thought Collective, 2009 Cambridge Harvard University Press Mitchell T. Fixing the Economy, Cultural Studies, 1998, vol. 12 (pg. 81-101)
- Mitchell T., Rule of Experts: Egypt, Techno-Politics, Modernity, 2002 Berkeley University of California Press
- Montecinos V., Markoff J., Economists in the Americas, 2010 Cheltenham, UK Edward Elgar Publishing
- Mudge SL, Vauchez A. Building Europe on a Weak Field: Law, Economics, and Scholarly Avatars in Transnational Politics, American Journal of Sociology, 2012, vol. 118 (pg. 449-492) (“Stephanie L. Mudge - Google Scholar”)
- Mudge S. What Is Neoliberalism? Socio-Economic Review, 2008, vol. 6 (pg. 703-731)
- Muniesa F., Millo Y., Callon M. An Introduction to Market Devices, Sociological Review, 2007, vol. 55 (pp. 1-12)
- National Research Council, Experimental Poverty Measures: Summary of a Workshop, 2005 Washington, DC National Academies Press
- National Research Council, Measuring Poverty: A New Approach, 1996 Washington, DC National Academies Press
- NBER Working Paper No. 18921
- Nelkin D. The Political Impact of Technical Expertise, Social Studies of Science, 1975, vol. 5 (pg. 35-54)
- Newell, R. (2011). Political Economy of Reform in Mexico (Richard Snape Lecture, 11 October)

Nik-Khah E. A Tale of Two Auctions,
Journal of Institutional Economics,
2008, vol. 4 (pg. 73-97)

Pederson, KR (1997). The Political
Economy of Distribution in
Developing Countries: A

Persson, T., & Tabellini, G. (1994). Is
Inequality Harmful for Growth?
American Economics

Rent-Seeking Approach. Public Choice.
91(3/4).351-373

Research Working Paper no.2443: World
Bank.

Transition. Journal of Economic Surveys.
19(2).263-293.

work? The Case of Central Bank
Independence. Brooking Papers on
Economic Activity. 2008.

Working Paper No.2610: Cambridge.